

Results and Discussion

The stoichiometric studies⁸⁻¹⁰ revealed that the complexes are binary [1 : 2, M : L] in nature.

Stability constants : The metal-ligand stepwise stability constants at pH 9.0 of these complexes were computed from the spectrophotometric data by Yatsimirskii's^{4,5} and Leden's⁶ methods in modified forms⁷.

The equilibrium constants thus obtained are reported in Table 1.

It is seen from Table 1 that the overall stability constants by these three methods agree with each other.

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Selectivity of Heterogeneous Ion-Exchange Membrane Discs with Reference to their Water Content, Porosity, Swelling, Electrolyte Absorption and Electrical Conductance

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IN heterogeneous membranes, the effect of binder cannot be ignored and so the study of some basic properties of the membrane becomes necessary. Michaelis¹ was the first to establish the standard electrochemical criteria for membrane characterisation, i.e., water content, porosity, swelling, electrolyte absorption and electrical conductivity.

Later Gregor^{2,3}, Wyllie⁴ and Hale⁵ reported on the characterisation of heterogeneous ion selective membranes. Recently, we have used the heterogeneous membranes of pyridinium molybdoarsenate⁶ (PMA) and rubidium⁷ and copper(II)⁸ tungstoarsenates (RbWA and CuWA) as ion selective electrodes. Present communication reports on the basic characteristics and its relationship with electrochemical performance of these heterogeneous ion exchanger membrane discs.

Experimental

Reagents and materials : All the reagents used were of analytical grade. Respective compounds, i.e., PMA, RbWA and CuWA and their heterogeneous membranes in Araldite were prepared as reported earlier⁶⁻⁹. Observations were made with two membranes of each exchanger.

Water content, porosity, swelling and electrolyte absorption^{2,5} : The membrane was kept immersed in a solution of 1 mol dm⁻³ NaCl for 24 hr to attain equilibrium. It was then taken out and the adhering electrolyte was wiped out. The thickness of this swollen membrane and its difference with that of dry membrane was taken as swelling. [An average value of the thicknesses measured carefully at different points of the membrane with a screw gauge (l.c.=0.001 cm) was taken as the thickness of the membrane]. The membrane was then washed several times with conductivity water and dried in a vacuum desiccator. The washings were collected to measure electrolyte absorption, conductometrically. The dried membrane was weighed to a constant weight and the difference in this weight (Ww) and the weight (Wd) of the membrane before immersing in the electrolyte solution divided by Ww was taken as water content. The porosity¹⁰ (ϵ) was calculated from the relationship,

$$\epsilon = \frac{Ww - Wd}{A.L. \rho w}$$

where A=area of the membrane, L=thickness of the membrane and ρw =density of water.

Conductance : The method recommended by Lakshminarayanaiah¹¹ was used for the determination of conductance of the membranes. The membrane was cemented between two half cells with the help of Araldite. It was then equilibrated by filling the half cells with 0.1 mol dm⁻³ NaCl solution. The solution was then replaced by mercury. The conductance was measured by connecting the Pt electrodes to the conductivity bridge.

Results and Discussion

When a heterogeneous membrane is immersed in water or electrolyte solution, water or solution may penetrate into the membrane structure occupying interstices which are present or which develop as a result of the difference between the swelling of

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TABLE 1—BASIC PROPERTIES OF HETEROGENEOUS ION EXCHANGER MEMBRANE DISCS OF PYRIDINIUM MOLYBDOARSENATE, RUBIDIUM TUNGSTOARSENATE AND COPPER TUNGSTOARSENATE

Exchanger Binder%	Membrane	Thickness of wet membrane mm	Thickness of dry membrane mm	Water content as % of the weight of wet membrane	Porosity %	Swelling mm	Electrolyte absorption NaCl g ⁻¹ wet membrane #g	Sp. conductivity milli mhos cm ⁻¹
PMA	I	1.145	1.061	7.7	11.5	0.084	32.3	4.89 × 10 ⁻⁵
35%	II	1.136	1.051	7.6	11.0	0.080	31.8	4.92 × 10 ⁻⁵
RbWA	I	0.860	0.712	8.5	19.1	0.148	51.0	1.00 × 10 ⁻³
30%	II	0.874	0.722	8.7	20.2	0.152	51.6	1.10 × 10 ⁻³
CuWA	I	0.970	0.775	9.3	22.0	0.195	61.5	4.07 × 10 ⁻³
30%	II	0.980	0.785	9.2	20.0	0.200	60.8	4.10 × 10 ⁻³

hydrophilic ion exchange resin and inert nonswelling binder (hydrophobic matrix). Gregor^{1,2} has pointed out that in heterogeneous membranes, there must be a thin film of water (resulting from interstices occupied by water or ion solution) between the hydrophilic resin particles and the surrounding hydrophobic matrix and that there are therefore two pathways for ion and water transport: (i) through the resin granules and their point of contact—a pathway of high selectivity, low water permeability and high electrical conductance and (ii) through the liquid film—of comparatively high ohmic resistance, zero selectivity and high water permeability.

It, therefore, follows that in a membrane having low values of porosity, water content and swelling, the amount of interstices available are less as compared to one having relatively larger values. Thus, the membrane with low value of porosity and swelling is expected to transport current through exchange sites only (the first pathway of high selectivity) and should, therefore, respond selectively to a particular ion. It appears that an inverse relationship should exist between the selectivity of a membrane and its swelling properties. The order of swelling, water content and porosity data for the membranes studied is CuWA > RbWA > PMA (Table 1). Thus, the PMA membrane being the least swelled, should act as highly selective electrode whereas CuWA as least selective. Our potential studies⁴⁻⁸ carried out on electrodes of these membranes do show such a behaviour and the selectivity order has been found to be PMA >> RbWA ≈ CuWA. Thus, our studies tend to show that an inverse relationship between swelling and selectivity for a membrane exists.

Electrolyte absorption studies of NaCl (Table 1) reveal that the amount of NaCl absorbed is maximum for CuWA membrane and minimum for PMA membrane. This is expected on the basis of porosity and swelling values of the membranes.

While recording membrane conductance, it was observed that the conductance changes slowly in the beginning and attains a constant value in about 5-7 min and thereafter remains constant. Such a behaviour points to negligible polarization on the mercury membrane faces.

The conductance values (Table 1) are found to be in the order CuWA > RbWA > PMA, which is consistent with the order of electrolyte absorption and swelling. When these membranes are equilibrated with 0.1M NaCl solution, the interstices which are already present or formed by the swelling of the exchanger particles, retain the electrolyte solution. Obviously, the conductance would depend on swelling as well as electrolyte uptake.

For CuWA membrane, the swelling and electrolyte uptake is largest and, therefore, it shows maximum conductance. In case of RbWA the values (swelling and electrolyte uptake) lie midway and so the conductance. For PMA membrane, both the values are lowest and hence the conductance.

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